

MASTER THESIS

**TIMELY DELIVERY OF GOODS IN CUSTOMER VIEW : A
STUDY ON FLIPKART**

***FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF
MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION***

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF
Prof. Sankar Mukherjee

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CERTIFICATE

Certificate from Faculty Guide

This is to certify that the project report (TIMELY DELIVERY OF GOODS IN CUSTOMER VIEW : A STUDY ON FLIPKART) has been prepared by Mr. ADITYA RAJ

DECLARATION

I, ADITYA RAJ, Adm No. 20GSOB2010109, student of MBA of School of Business, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, hereby declare that the project report on (TIMELY DELIVERY OF GOODS IN CUSTOMER VIEW : A STUDY ON FLIPKART) is an original and authenticated work done by me.

I further declare that it has not been submitted elsewhere by any other person in any of the institutes for the award of any degree.

ADITYA RAJ

Date: -

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I would like to give warmest gratefulness to my faculty mentor and supervisor **Prof. Sankar Mukherjee** for bringing the weight of his considerable experience and knowledge to this research work named “***TIMELY DELIVERY OF GOODS IN CUSTOMER VIEW : A STUDY ON FLIPKART***”. His continuous guidance and fetching out the most relevant and practical topic for the research so that I can grind my own knowledge. I perceive as this opportunity as a big milestone in my career development. I will strive to use gained skills and knowledge in the best possible way, and I will continue to work on their improvement, in order to attain desired career objectives. Hope to continue cooperation with good people in future. As we have come to our end journey of being a professional course, this project will add on more value to my professional life coming ahead. This research work will emphasis towards the current scenario of the market and polish my understanding of various issues and problems faced by general public. I will make sure to gain that learning in this project that will enhance my knowledge and area of specialization.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

(1) Research problem- since the beginning of the online platforms for buying goods, one major problem was to maintain timely delivery, since the market and customers of India were fond of going out in the market and purchasing goods, so if any goods delivery company takes longer to deliver the goods to them, the customers will not connect with the business and will make no profit. Cpd or customer promised date or timely delivery and fast delivery plays a major role in connecting and sustaining in the market.

(2) Methodology- the research methodology used is a mix of primary research and secondary research. Majorly, primary research data are collected on self-references and experience during my internship in the Flipkart. Secondary data are collected through online sites and Wikipedia which had data of previous year surveys regarding the importance of timely delivery of goods.

(3) Key results- the key result or finding from this research is that, the online shopping platforms like Flipkart keep too much emphasis on timely delivery of goods to maintain their customer base & satisfaction of customers. Flipkart warehouse like “e-kart” works in the best possible way to maintain cpd. Customer promised date delivery is seen as among most important marketing requirement, as the earlier the delivery, the more customer would order the product. As after ordering the good/product, the customer doesn't want to wait much and wants the product to reach the soonest possible. So, timely delivery is seen as a very important thing in my research.

(4) Conclusion -concluding to the entire process, this was a necessary analysis to be done, and collection of data to the results will help us understand more about the importance of timely delivery and what Flipkart do to maintain that as well as improve the cpd or customer promised date or timely delivery. Also, the study shows the everyday challenges faced by Flipkart to avoid cpd breach, unnecessary delay, and delivery faults like delivering to wrong address etc, along with it maintaining timely delivery during festivals and rush hours and to keep up the user experience by delivering fastest. The concepts of next day delivery, 24 hour delivery, etc in tier 1 cities and making the product reach in the remotest village on time. This is indeed challenging but this literature will talk on all aspects of timely delivery to customers by Flipkart and how they achieve this. The customer-centric approach of this literature will be useful for the reader to understand the processes

INTRODUCTION

FLIPKART

Flipkart Private Limited is an Indian e-commerce company established in 2007. It started with a primary focus on online book sales and soon, expanded to lifestyle products, electronics, home essentials and groceries. Today, Flipkart is the biggest online Indian marketplace competing with the world leader Amazon. Since 2010, the company has made a number of acquisitions including Letsbuy, Myntra, Jabong, eBay India, etc. In addition to its main office in Bengaluru, Flipkart has branch offices at Delhi and Mumbai. Apart from India, the firm is registered in Singapore. In 2018, the US-based retail chain Walmart acquired majority stake in Flipkart.

Recently, Flipkart has opened its R&D centre at Israel. This is in line with its latest acquisition of Israeli start-up Upstream Commerce. The centre is run by talented engineers from across the world.

Headquarters

Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

Key People:

Kalyan Krishnamurthy – CEO

Sachin Bansal & Binny Bansal – Founders

Logo:

Flipkart uses a single alphabet 'f' in blue color on a yellow-colored shopping bag. The alphabet 'f' is accompanied by speed lines. It is meant to denote positive and quick service. The chosen colors signify imaginativeness, liveliness and inclusivity. The name 'Flipkart' itself means 'Flipping things into kart'. Till now, the company has modified its logo 5-6 times.

Revenue:

US \$6.1 billion (FY 2019)

Number of Employees: 30,000

Official Website: www.flipkartcareers.com

Achievements:

In 2014, Flipkart became the first Indian online retailer to achieve \$1.9 billion GMV (Gross Merchandise Value).

Co-founder Sachin Bansal was named 'Entrepreneur of the Year 2012–2013' by The Economic Times.

Flipkart's app became the first Indian mobile app to cross 50 million users in 2016.

ONLINE DELIVERY

The Importance of Delivery Service in E-commerce

When you're running an e-commerce business, one thing you absolutely need to get right is delivery. Customer's needs have changed dramatically, with most now expecting a fast, reliable delivery service.

If you're looking to improve your customer service and boost your business, paying attention to your delivery process is key. Here, you'll discover why delivery service is so important in e-commerce and how to ensure it's the best that it can be.

Why is delivery so important?

Delivery of goods used to take 7-10 working days, with very few options available to customers. However, as technology has evolved, so too have the number of delivery methods and options.

Customers today have a lot of choice when it comes to receiving the goods they buy online. This has led to a total change in attitude towards how delivery should work. Next day deliveries aren't just a perk anymore, they're actually expected. So, if your business isn't providing a variety of delivery options, it could be missing out on a lot of potential customers.

Delivery is also the last impression a customer has of your business. So, if they experience a problem, it's going to leave them with a negative view of your brand, and they'll be unlikely to buy from you again.

There is even businesses offering same-day delivery in specific geographic locations. This delivery expansion is occurring in both the US and the UK with increased focus from the online grocery market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- Understand the importance of timely delivery of goods
- Understand how e-commerce companies achieve it
- Current processes running in the e-commerce company

SIGNIFICANCE & RELEVANCE OF STUDY

The quality of product sold is not under direct control of flipkart, but delivering them on time and in case of any defect, returning the order, receiving the returned order and sending it back to the seller is in the hands of flipkart. So customer centric approach on timely delivery has better and very important significance and also is relevant for study

Customers are the most important factor in e-commerce businesses and therefore customer satisfaction must be the main priority in everything you do. This is no different when providing a delivery service. Customers want communication from the beginning of their experience. This includes offering clear delivery service options on the website and acknowledgement of the order after purchase on screen and via email. Customers rely on updates and this highlights to them that a company cares about them receiving their delivery. Deliveries can lead to a customer planning their day around it, so providing a time slot for delivery can ensure customers are satisfied with their experience and will shop with you again.

In e-commerce, your reputation is everything. When you provide a poor-quality delivery service, it's going to have a significantly negative impact on your reputation. Social media allows consumers to vent their anger, so ensuring you don't offer a poor delivery service is as important as ever. Even if just one customer writes a negative review about your delivery service, it's going to put off other people from buying from you. So, if you're looking to become successful, it's crucial you follow the tips above and work on improving your delivery service as much as you can.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Capstone Project-Ivery case study FLIPKART Logistics

Finally, solutions and strategies have evaluated and further demonstrated with individual implementation plans. Moreover, a description of strategies relating to the development of sustainability and financial value has illustrated. "The key supply chain challenges online retailers are lack of authenticity of the product and suppliers, outsourcing of third-party suppliers, increased cost of shipping, and disrupted quick delivery." (SCCG, 2020) The issues we identified are increased shipping cost, higher dependency on other logistics companies, Disruption in last-mile delivery Also, impact analysis with a relative root-cause analysis had assessed. Also, there are different opportunities have identified for future opportunities that are flourishing online gro

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- Research Design
- Research Process
- Data collection
 - Samples size
- Errors in the study
- Scope and the Limitation of the study

Research Methodology

The research process consists of stages or steps leading to a project from its consideration of final analysis, recommendations and final actions. The research process provides a structured way and ensures that all aspects of the research project are consistent. Research studies change with a series of steps, each representing an answer to an important question.

RESEARCH DESIGN

I suggest that I first conduct a second in-depth study to understand the full impact and vision of the sector, to review and analyze industry policies and reports, in which specific issues will be selected, which I feel should not be addressed or need to be changed. This section will help me limit and select only the most important question and issue, which remains in growth and division in the industry. The various tasks I have performed in the research design process are:

- Defining the information need
- Design the exploratory, descriptive and causal research

. RESEARCH PROCESS

The research process has four distinct but consistent steps for research analysis with a logical structure and sequence: Determination of information research problem.

- Development of appropriate research design.
- Execution of research design.
- Communication of results.

Each step is considered a separate process that involves a combination of task, step and process. The steps taken are logical, purposeful, organized, honest, legitimate, inhuman and persistent.

EXPLORATORY RESEARCH

The method, I used for exploratory research was Secondary data

SECONDARY DATA

Information already available elsewhere, has been collected for another purpose. Sources include census reports, commercial publications, and registration services. There are two types of secondary data: secondary internal and external data. Data compiled within or outside the organization for a specific purpose other than current research information, which has already been published? Market data is compiled for purposes other than the current research effort; it could be internal data, such as existing sales tracking information, or it could be research conducted by someone else. The secondary source of data used is books and websites My suggestion is that I first conduct a second in-depth study to understand the full impact and vision of the industry, to review and analyze industry policies and reports, in which specific issues will be selected, which I feel should not be addressed or should be changed.

DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH STEPS

in the descriptive research: Statement of the problem

- Identifying the information needed to solve the problem
- Selection or development of instruments for gathering the information
- Identification of target population and determination of sampling Plan.
- Develop a data collection process
- Collection of information
- Analysis of information
- Generalization and / or forecasting

DATA COLLECTION

Data collection took place with the help of questionnaires. The questionnaire came down to the most widely used and cost-effective method of data collection. A common feature of all types of questionnaires is the reliance on oral responses to questions, written or oral. Determination of the sample plan and sample size.

TARGET POPULATION

It is a description of the characteristics of that group of people where the course is intended. He tries to describe them as they are rather than the interpreter wants them to be. Also called audiences. A certain number of people targeted as beneficiaries of the program. This will be all or a small group of potential users, such as youth, women, residents, or locals. Areas entitled: Governance, Accountability and Evaluation, Performance Management and Leadership. The number of people to be reached through a particular action or intervention; can refer to groups with specific characteristics of people or places. A group of people you are trying to reach by a specific strategy or activity The number of people referred to is the number I want to make a good case; sample frames to match the number of people identified. A specific set of resources that is the object or victim of an investigation. Audience is defined by age, background, ability, and preferences, among other things, the purpose of a particular subject.

ERRORS IN THE STUDY

Interviewer error There is bias in the negotiators in the form of questions. Open-ended questions may be discriminated against by the interviewer's views or by examination, as the interviewers guide the respondent during the completion of the questionnaire. The attitude discussed by the respondent to the respondent during the interview can greatly affect their level of interest and willingness to respond openly. As interviewers, assessment and clarification enhance respondents' understanding and produce holistic responses, these benefits are removed by the problems of seeking fame, social curiosity, and favoritism.

Questionnaire error The design of the questionnaire should be careful so that only the required data is disclosed and no unwanted data is generated. Questions should be carefully worded so that questions do not load up and lead to the mind of the respondent .

Response error Respondents selected for interview were not always available and willing to work together and, in many cases, respondents were found to lack the knowledge, opinion, attitudes or facts required in addition to uninformed response errors and response styles also led to survey errors.

Research Design The design of a study is a conceptual framework in which research is conducted. The research design is a detailed program used to guide research designed for its intended purpose. It is a list of advanced decision-making conclusions that have a key strategy or research model to align with research objectives. The design of the research is necessary because it facilitates the navigation of various research activities, thus making the research as efficient as possible and obtaining high- quality information with minimal effort, time and money.

CONCEPTUALIZATION

OVERVIEW

Simply speaking, on-time delivery is the ability of businesses to meet the customers' demands and deliver the services or products to the customers punctually. It sounds easy as pie, but it weights.

THE IMPORTANCE OF ON-TIME DELIVERY

Deliver to the right people, right places and right on time

You must have replayed enough to learn by heart a hit song of a man standing in front of the church powerlessly lost her woman for just arriving 25 minutes too late. It was a heartbreaking story of the previous decade on being late a few minutes, on the other side, things happen similarly to e-commerce today. A lot of things in this world are partial, but the priceless gift that everybody might own equally is 24 hours per day. And perhaps, hardly a person could long to throw such a precious day of their life to do nothing than wait for shippers. Too many things have been said on the importance of on time delivery to the point it seems as plain as no more than a theory of being punctual to people who already know how exactly it influences on brand's prestige, reputation and reliability, as well as customers' satisfactory, yet stay conform with thousands of orders arriving late every day in practice.

EXAMINE WHY DELIVERY SERVICE IS IMPORTANT?

Walk in the shoes of KFC, the fast-food giant, coped with a disastrous crisis that never happened in its history, of more than 800 in 900 of its outlets in UK had been temporarily closed in early 2018, where the heart of the problem coming from nowhere than their delivery firm, DHL. An incident to its storage depot system leading to distribution interruption turned out a big fat chaos as the delivery was failed to supply enough chicken to the restaurants and heavily disrupted the chain operation. KFC eventually faced with strong public complaint and disappointed reactions all over England as well as hundreds critics from financial news worldwide, pushing KFC to the hardest wobbling weeks ever in its business, proving by the declined number in its revenue- approximately 1 million Pounds loss per day. Indeed, delivery failures could get you into enduring loud consequences if taken lightly. In short, you need to build a shipping system or outsource to a credit name in logistic industry.

ON TIME IS ABOUT CUSTOMER AND MONEY

Goods/services quality and Delivery services as like two non splittable faces of One Coin – the Value of Ecommerce products today

The quality of ecommerce product should comprise of the inherent good values and delivery services. Poor delivery services are server as you sell a low quality product. That may lead you to customer and money lost, you may think of it like a norm “customers may come and go and the new one awaits”, and you still have other chances of conversion. But due to the seeding of online reviews and rating sites, customers’ voices are heard by other customers. If they turn their back on your services, that trust soon gone to your rivals and your business may evaporate rapidly.

Therefore, the adherence to delivery date and promise time becomes more influencing than ever to the existence of ecommerce companies, particularly Magento stores, and in general, its competitive ability within their world. Those who cannot meet the assumption delivery date have long way to reach its potential success.

Discover the definite benefits that on-time delivery brings about in the following part.

INTENSIFY SATISFACTION

The constantly on-time fulfillment gradually builds up customers’ reliability, thus, through service – branding works well than other PR opportunities.

Their satisfaction tends to drive them to share their positive ratings and reviews on the products through different channels, to bounce back to increase their credibility. On the long run the companies win loyalty and support from their customers as true friends.

DRAG NEW CUSTOMERS

With new customers, punctual delivery is marked as the first test, a fundamental requirement under any circumstances. Delivery is also the first direct interaction between a new customer and the company beside the inherent good values. Companies of punctual shipments will have good impressions and open gates to other transactions with customers.

ENHANCE EFFICIENCY

Delivery on-time could mean every procedure of delivery parts perform rhythmically: from its distribution of storage, the logistics plans – means of transportation & assigning routes, realistic delivery schedule and management, to the right personnel in-charge. Otherwise, there are illogical elsewhere that the company should make alterations and amendments as quick as possible if they meet difficulties in deliveries.

WRAP-UP

In a nutshell, on-time delivery only does good deeds for eCommerce companies. You can refer to Magento 2 Delivery Date extension that help you to know customers' desired delivery time and prevent delivery failure.

Moreover, we advise company to build a close partnership with reputed logistic services, the other way to accomplish this concern is to establish an efficient shipping system on your own, which brings further benefits for you.

Now, you will get your Flipkart orders in under 90 minutes, at least in select cities. Walmart-owned e-commerce platform has taken another chance on the hyperlocal delivery space, by launching Flipkart Quick, a 90-minute delivery. The service will initially start in six cities, starting with Bengaluru. Flipkart Quick will have more than 2,000 products in categories such as Grocery, Fresh, Dairy, Meat, Mobiles, Electronics Accessories, Stationery Items and Home Accessories in the first phase.

The customers will have the option to choose between the next 90 minutes or book a 2-hour slot as per their convenience. Customers can place orders any time of the day, and get their orders delivered between 6 am to midnight; starting with a minimum delivery fee Rs 29.

"This is a great model for India as households of all sizes are already used to their neighbourhood Kirana stores. While we start with our dark store (no-walk-in) model, wherein we enable sellers to store inventory close to the consumer; this model has the potential of encouraging local entrepreneurship and enabling new business strategies and partnerships", said Sandeep Karwa, Vice-President, Flipkart.

You order an iPhone7 on Flipkart on the last day of the Big Billion Days (BBD) sale — October 7 — at 7pm and it is delivered the same evening. Even a year ago, this speed of delivery would have seemed impossible to achieve. But Flipkart has been around long enough to plan well and make it happen. They had a troublesome BBD in 2014, a better one in 2015, and come 2016 they have established clear leadership during Diwali sales, clocking a record Rs 1,400 crore on a single day, the biggest in the history of Indian retail. An [efficient supply chain](#) was among their strengths this time. Reducing costs and delivering faster — two tangentially opposite targets — were achieved after 9–10 months of planning by the engineering and design teams.

Neeraj Aggarwal

E-commerce in India has long been struggling with supply chain management. The scale is even higher during festive sales. Not only is the volume of orders higher, but expectations to deliver quickly are also high, especially for high-ticket items. Neeraj Aggarwal, VP of Operations at Flipkart says: “Festive season sales come with complexities. [During Dussehra and Durga Puja](#), staffs are often unavailable. Customers may not be available as they might be on holiday. So we had to push our entire system to the brink — right from technology to availability of manpower — to a whole new level to push the boundaries of the supply chain.”

Discounts, selection, fast delivery

Customers love large selections and discounts, but a superlative experience comes with fast delivery. If tough times are the real test of character for man, the festive season is the test for the e-commerce supply chain. But this being [Flipkart's third BBD sale](#), they were well prepared. On October 12, they

carried out 7,00,000 shipments. From October 3–16, high-value products [those above Rs 5,000] were delivered five days faster across all pin codes than in 2015.

Flipkart cooperates with Delhivery, Ecom Express, and Blue Dart too. But Ekart claims to cover larger geographies than third-party players. Along with the COD availability, faster delivery also helped Flipkart gain more customers. Neeraj is keen to add that customer experience in remote parts was also important to them. For superior service, Flipkart was particular about the last-mile experience. “We got feedback on delivery boys by SMS from customers for improving our performance. We got a high score for the two weeks during festive sales,” claims Neeraj.

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Reliability comes with keeping promises. The delivery date guaranteed to the customer was treated with utmost importance. “We were able to get 150 basis points better than last year, thanks to better speed of delivery,” says Neeraj.

More clients, more complexities

Ekart had started serving third parties a few months ago. Currently, they cater to offline players as well as online players like [Myntra](#), [Jabong](#), [Voonik](#), Hopscotch, Paytm, and Yepme among others. “This was our first test since externalisation. It comes with more complexities. During Dussehra holidays, packages were piling up as consumers were not available. Many delivery staff also took off for the festive days,” says Neeraj.

Yet, the cost of the supply chain was reduced by 35 percent from last year. Neeraj says this happened due to their internal teams’ hard work during the last one year in improving productivity. Developing channels to invoke whatever capacity is there to deliver to customers was the main goal. In alternative channels, [Ekart has tied up with Apollo pharmacy](#) stores and kiranas to let their customers pick up packages from there, across more than 40 cities in the country. “Understanding geography and the high-density pockets were crucial to figure out better models including our alternative delivery methods (ADM) without costing too much,” says Neeraj.

Both Snapdeal and Amazon have more warehouses than Flipkart [Flipkart:18, Amazon: 27, Snapdeal: 69], but Neeraj believes that the number doesn't matter. "We have had seven years' experience in inventory strategies, accurately planning the volume of orders that would come from each region, and which warehouses will have to cater to that, etc.," he says.

This year, Flipkart had 50 percent more storage space than last year without *really* increasing the warehouses. "We experimented with flexible storage methods. A lot of the design team's effort went into ensuring flexible storage," says Neeraj. He adds that the aim was to augment the productivity of manpower. Expenditure on infrastructure reduced significantly as it was done last year. The technology was also done last year, so the engineering team did not have to build a lot, Neeraj claims.

Time is money

When the iPhone7 was launched on the last day of the BBD sale, 99 percent delivery was done on the same day before midnight. An extra 10,000 boys were hired to work across supply chain at Flipkart during the festive season.

“We were not short of delivery boys. We accurately planned how many were needed in each city. We ensured they got time off to spend with their families, and also offered incentives to ensure availability,” claims Neeraj. On an average day, only half the trucks are needed for the transport compared to those during Diwali.

Omni-channel strategy added capacity and reduced costs for Flipkart. Kiranas that are associated with them took care of delivery in the residential complexes in their area, except for large appliances. Flipkart’s ADM are operational in more than 40 cities now.

A competent logistics network is an inevitable part of a functional e-commerce ecosystem. If Flipkart’s claims of success are true, this could be a model that can be emulated by its peers and competitors as well as aspiring players in the market.

WAREHOUSE

A warehouse is a place where products or materials can get stored before they move to another location. It's a crucial element to your supply chain management. And some types of warehouses get used and designed for different reasons.

A warehouse can help with inventory tracking, shipping costs and meeting customer demands. Having your warehouse set up properly makes the flow of materials more efficient.

There are different types of warehouse design out there depending on the [needs of your business](#). Certain warehouses require special HVAC systems or specialized equipment. Here are a few different types of warehouses.

- **General Warehouse:** a basic storage facility for items that don't need climate control or a specialized environment
- **Distribution Center:** a warehouse where a large number of products or raw materials are then sent to retailers or wholesalers
- **Fulfillment Warehouse:** a type of warehouse where online purchases will get picked, packed and shipped
- **Automated Warehouse:** fully-automated robotic systems can execute all the processes
- **Climate-Controlled:** if some items or products need to get refrigerated or kept at a certain temperature

Different warehouses are going to provide a varying range of functionality.

What Elements Are Included in a Warehouse?

There are a lot of moving parts that go into the organization of a warehouse. You need to know exactly what type of products will get stored and the most efficient place to store them. The flow of the materials and the space that's available to store them are important factors to consider.

You also need to take into account the number and size of the racks or storage equipment that is needed. The space that gets assigned for each area needs to be suitable for the product that will get stored. When this happens, you can have improved inventory accuracy.

Having an efficient warehouse will also contribute to a reduction in overhead costs. When you improve how the warehouse operates you can make better

staffing decisions. You are also able to lower the level of risk of damaged or misplaced products.

There are a few main elements of a warehouse that can get used to help with the different [areas of your business](#). They can include:

- Storage systems for quick access and efficient processing
- Inventory management software to track the inventory coming into the warehouse and going out
- Staff to make sure the processes are getting completed efficiently
- Climate control for any products that need to stay at a certain temperature
- Equipment to move products to and from your warehouse

Key Takeaways

Different types of businesses will require different types of warehouse processes. If you run a distribution center that only deals with footwear, then you won't need a climate-controlled warehouse. And if you operate a fulfillment center, then an assembly line setup probably wouldn't work well for your needs.

Essentially, a warehouse is a place to store products before or after they get sent to a separate location. For example, a distribution center might hold inventory for a fulfillment center. If customer demand increases and the inventory is low, they can place an order with the distribution center.

Are you looking into building a new warehouse to expand your business or keep up with customer demand? Take a look into your business operations and identify the main areas that could get improved with a warehouse. This will allow you to gather the right information to decide which type of warehouse will work best for your needs.

It's also important to keep in mind the different elements that go into a warehouse. They will vary depending on the type of warehouse you have, but they serve the same purpose regardless. They get put in place to help supply chain operations and streamline employee workflow.

To manage heavy operations, Flipkart has its own logistics and supply chain company named "E-kart" which helps in timely delivery of goods and maintain cpd or the customer promised date.

EKART

EKART is India's largest logistics and supply chain company delivering 10 million shipments a month to 3800+ pin codes. Established in 2009, EKART as Flipkart's in-house supply chain arm has powered the growth of Flipkart with innovations such as Cash on Delivery, In-a-day guarantee (50 cities), Same-day guarantee (13 cities).

EKART delivers on a consistent excellence in consumer experience by delivering reliably and managing variability at scale.

With a renewed mission of transforming core supply chain through technology, EKART is now offering the same proposition to Brands, Sellers, Platforms and Consumers outside of the Flipkart Group.

Ekart Logistics is one of the many private delivery service companies that can be found in India. Due to the sheer size of India, it is no wonder companies like Ekart Logistics excel in their services and the capacity of their operations. In this article, you will get all the pertinent information on a company like Ekart Logistics.

What is Ekart Logistics?

Ekart Logistics is a privately held company that offers parcel and mail delivery services. It is a relatively new company since it was created in

2009, as a subsidiary of another delivery service company known as Flipkart. For this reason, Ekart Logistics tracking service is very similar to the one of Flipkart.

It is headquartered in the city of Bangalore, Karnataka. Unlike other companies, Ekart Logistics not only delivers mail but also handles shipments of products purchased through Flipkart.

The company is highly valued for the quality of its customer service. Ekart Logistics courier tracking service can be managed by phone calls, where customers can get up-to-date information on the shipping status of their packages or correspondence.

Although it was founded in 2009, it was not until 2012 that the company diversified its operations and concentrated all its efforts to offer good quality postal delivery services. According to a recent study, the company handles more than 10 million deliveries nationwide.

Ekart Logistics courier tracking service allows tracking deliveries to more than 50 regions and cities in the country. This means that the company has the operational capacity to offer services to any destination in India, including the most remote regions.

How do I track my Ekart parcel?

Like Flipkart's tracking system, Ekart Logistics tracking is simple and easy to use. While the system does not provide a large amount of shipment information, the information is always up to date.

Users can use the Ekart Logistics courier tracking service through the virtual platform found on the official website, or via text messages. Also, as mentioned above, users can track their packages or correspondence by asking customer service.

It is important to note that the tracking service is only available once users have obtained the Ekart Logistics tracking number. The tracking number is sent via email and text messages once users complete all the necessary paperwork.

What is Ekart tracking ID?

The tracking and tracing ID is another name by which the Ekart Logistics tracking number is known. This tracking number is a combination of numeric and alphabetic characters.

However, unlike other companies that integrate the tracking number digitally, the Ekart Logistics tracking number is printed manually on packages and mail. The tracking number is characterized by 4 alphabetic characters and 10 numeric characters.

It is important to mention that the combination of characters is related to the postal code of the destination. It is an efficient way to manage and control the tracking of parcels or mail.

Due to the size of the country, it is common for users to misplace the tracking number. In this specific case, users can access a special help section with the Ekart Logistics customer care number, with which they can consult the tracking number in case they need it.

Where can Ekart deliver?

At present, the company only has the operational capacity to operate on a national level. Given the sheer size of the country, a huge infrastructure is needed to operate in all regions of India. For this reason, the company has no international operations for the time being.

However, it contributes to Flipkart's international subsidiaries, such as Klick2Shop Logistics Services International, which is based in Singapore and ships throughout Asia. As a contribution, the company uses customer service resources to support Flipkart's allied subsidiaries.

How long does it take for Ekart to deliver?

Delivery times may change depending on the destination and the type of service requested by the customer. With the standard delivery service, the approximate delivery time is 4 to 5 working days.

With the express service, Ekart Logistics delivery time is 2 to 3 business days, regardless of the destination. It is worth noting that users receive a text message with the estimated delivery time.

Users can check delivery time and use the Ekart Logistics tracking service to obtain more detailed information through a mobile application that can be downloaded from the official website.

Does Ekart Logistics deliver on Sunday?

This is one of the company's most valued attributes. Users can receive their packages or mail on Sundays. By consulting with Ekart Logistics contact numbers, users can even arrange for deliveries on holidays.

Ekart Logistics contact is available on the company's official website. You can interact with customer service through phone calls or text messages.

Is Ekart Logistics shipping expensive?

Being a Flipkart subsidiary, shipping costs are usually much cheaper compared to those offered by competitors. Ekart Logistics shipping fees may vary depending on package dimensions, destination, and type of service.

For packages or mail weighing less than one kilogram, the average shipping cost is \$2.00. It is important to clarify that this average shipping cost is for the standard service.

For packages weighing more than one kilogram, the approximate shipping cost is 5 dollars.

With the express service, packages weighing less than one kilogram are delivered at a shipping cost of approximately US\$4.

For packages weighing more than one kilogram, the shipping cost is approximately US\$6. In case you need it, you can use the Ekart Logistics customer care number for more information.

How do I contact Ekart?

Users can access Ekart Logistics contact through the official website. On the website (<https://ekartlogistics.com/>), users have access to email or the company's official networks, such as Instagram, Facebook, or Twitter.

Ekart Logistics is India's largest private postal company. Thanks to its operations, millions of users can manage parcels or mail shipments virtually every day. It is also instrumental in enabling companies like Flipkart to operate efficiently in the country.

CUSTOMER PROMISED DATE (CPD)

Delivering products on promised date is very essential for trust making with the customer, flipkart ensures cpd is achieved in order for timely delivery of goods.

Other major competitors are also working effectively in order to meet the on time delivery of goods or in other words, customer promised date delivery. A major secondary source study representing the importance, way, and techniques of on time delivery is being presented.

Amazon has been a major disruptor in the industry and changed consumer perception by delivering shipments within the promised 2 days. The operational efficiencies required to run Amazon's distribution centers is no joke. Other retail giants have now been forced to follow suit and meet the high standards set by Amazon. The expectation of on-time delivery is now more than ever before in traditional industries such as chemical, pharmaceutical and distribution. Here are a few KPIs that are critical to measure delivery performance in Logistics and Supply Chain operations –

- On-time Delivery (OTD) also referred to as On-time Performance (OTP), Shipped-on-Time (SOT) or Delivery on Time (DOT)
- DIF – Delivery in Full
- DIFOT – Delivery In Full on Time
- Inventory Turns (days)
- Costs as a percentage of sales

This article contains real-life experiences of a general manager and executive of a chemical company. We will discuss the key contributors to on-time delivery and how by starting with a low percentage of OTD you can achieve significant gains over time.

The realization

- You are responsible for managing operations and see some glaring issues. However, you are not able to pinpoint the precise problem or

where to even start. You request Key Performance Indicator data (“KPI”) from different departments.

- As you begin your review, you notice a lack of focus – i.e., there are several KPIs, all being portrayed as having an equal value. One logistics KPI stands out: The On-time Delivery (“OTD”) percentage within the company is only 76%. Upon reflection, you realize efficiency can be enhanced by managing operations with this single measure.
- In this blog, we will elaborate why OTD is so important. This single KPI can drive tangible value for your customer and totally change how customers perceive you. Our next blog in the same series expands on the problem/opportunity you inherited, the steps you can take to produce rapid positive results and finally the result achieved.

Sales Order Number	Customer Promise Date	Actual Delivery Date	On-Time Delivery	OTD %
12345	Dec 1, 2018	Dec 1, 2018	Yes	75%
23456	Dec 10, 2018	Dec 15, 2018	No	
45678	Dec 21, 2018	Dec 21, 2018	Yes	
56789	Dec 24, 2018	Dec 24, 2018	Yes	

What is OTD?

OTD is a metric used to assess the ability of a business in fulfilling the shipment order within the period of promised delivery date.

On-time Delivery (OTD) – The Logistics KPI Defined

The On-time delivery performance refers to the ratio of customer order lines shipped on or before the requested delivery date / customer promised date

versus the total number of order lines. This is usually expressed as a percentage and can be calculated for several measurement periods.

FIGURE 1: THE PROCEDURE OF ORDER FULFILLMENT TO ENSURE ON-TIME DELIVERY (OTD)

What is required to Deliver On-time?

1. **1.**You have forecasted estimated demand, ran MRP and ordered materials. You create a purchase order for the required materials.
2. **2.**The materials are received, recorded and put into your raw material stores area.
3. **3.**An order has been received, you check available inventory, determine that you can produce the order and promise your customer delivery on a specific date.
4. **4.**You create a work order and issue it to production.
5. **5.**The materials are correctly picked, moved to the production area and produced.
6. **6.**Inventory is yielded and quality confirms that the produced inventory meets product specifications.
7. **7.**Inventory is put-away to the finished good-storage location.
8. **8.**Per customer promised date, inventory is picked and delivered to the shipping dock where proper shipping documentation is prepared. In chemical or pharmaceutical companies, shipping documentation typically includes other documentation such as Certificate of Analysis (COA), SDS etc.
9. **9.**The delivery is scheduled, the truck arrives to take the finished goods away and the delivery arrives on-time and undamaged.
10. **10.**You just executed the perfect On-time Delivery and, most importantly, your customer is happy that you met their expectations.

Why is OTD Important?

- On time delivery drives better collaboration with your customers, ensures reliability of delivery and most importantly customer loyalty.
- 35** • Customers expect you to meet the promised delivery date. It is important to set the right expectations with your customers and meet

them. If you can't meet your customer's expectation and deliver on time then they will find a supplier who can.

- Consistent problems with on-time delivery will not only disrupt your business or result in loss of reputation but will also affect many other areas of a company's supply chain and can irreparably damage customer relationship and long-term success.

How to deliver on time?

- Understand and track the late delivery reasons, analyse the various factors that contribute to late delivery and identify the root cause.
- After identifying the root cause and the issues in late delivery, prioritize the issues and focus on the actionable steps to success.
- Develop a plan and implement it.
- Monitor results and revise the plan accordingly.

Reasons for late deliveries

With that in mind, think about all the things that can go wrong. The occurrence of any one of the following errors will result in late delivery. Most companies use a [Customer Relationship Management \(“CRM”\) system](#) to track and resolve customer complaints. If you are a pharmaceutical customer, the emphasis on quality is significantly higher therefore imperative to manage these inefficiencies a lot closer.

- Bad forecasts
- Sales over-promising
- Incorrect lead-times and safety stock levels
- Purchase order errors
- Supplier delays
- Inventory inaccuracy

- Receiving data entry and put-away errors
- Production picking errors
- Bad standard operating procedures (“SOPs”)
- Production operator errors
- Maintenance and equipment related issues
- Quality delays
- Product rejections
- Material handling put-away errors
- Shipping department picking and packing errors
- Shipping documentation inaccuracy
- Delivery scheduling and late pickup
- Damage in transit and late delivery, etc.
- Customer changing orders constantly without a proper procedure in place
- Customer’s inability to handle products received in full – This could be due to lack of storage space, personnel or any other intrinsic reasons etc.

The OTD percentage is a holistic measure of operational performance. It measures an organization’s ability to manage its supply chain in a predictable manner. If you live up to the promises you make, you create value for your customer.

FIGURE 2: METRICS THAT MATTER IN ON-TIME DELIVERY

Success Story 1

One of our clients, a US-based chemical firm lacked the [inventory management software](#) and barcode to line out its full inventory of warehouse and manufacturing facility. To provide an effective solution, Xcelpros designed a new bar code scanning technology for the company along with durable, custom labels to improve data capturing and enhance operational efficiency with an ‘integrated material requirement planning system’.

It took us three weeks to give a closure to the entire label installation process without causing any disruption to the live operational environment. We successfully lined-out the warehouse, and the results were great.

- Eliminating manual data transcription reduced the scope of error
- Automating the procedure helped to minimize the time in materials management
- Limiting the frequency of materials-related changes in the production schedule

The chemical company now functions at close to 95% on-time delivery, a 30% increase in operational efficiency—with a 20% reduction in inventory.

FIGURE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF WAREHOUSE OPERATING COST

Success Story 2

We had to come up with a technological solution for arranging on-time delivery at multiple distribution centers for a client. Managing this complex grid of network to successfully manufacture and deliver the products on time demanded continuous monitoring of production facilities, logistics hubs and consolidation points.

We came up with a supply chain visibility model using advanced analytics to track the order status in the supply chain. We developed a dashboard and reorganized the orders with a clustering approach as per source, delivery destination, stock keeping units (SKUs) etc so that the status of the each individual product is tracked. Following this methodology gave our client a complete visibility on their product status and delivery performance. The real-time data generated better insight across the supply chain, and corrective measures were taken on an immediate basis to manage the impact of late delivery.

FIGURE 4: ANALYSIS OF INSUFFICIENT LEAD TIME GIVEN TO THE SUPPLIER

Source: <http://www.scielo.org.za/pdf/sajie/v28n4/09.pdf>

Figure 4 depicts the analysis of insufficient lead time given to the supplier. The root cause of this insufficient lead time is the delay and long-stretched process – from the material requirement planning (MRP) to purchase request (PR), to purchase order (PO).

FIGURE 5: ANALYSIS FOR SUPPLIER DELAY

Source: <http://www.scielo.org.za/pdf/sajie/v28n4/09.pdf>

Figure 5 analyzes the key reasons behind supplier delay, which need to be addressed. It pinpoints “no tracking control” to be the prime reason that causes supplier delay.

One of the major concerns here is how to keep a track of MRP-PO-PR conversion if you don't have any component for tracking control. This lack of monitoring brings operational inefficiency due to which there has been a gap between the agreed time and the actual time of delivering the components. They are found to be the major bottlenecks in achieving OTR and thus OTD.

The solution is to develop and design a lean live tracking (LLT) system for the ease of monitoring with very low manual intervention. It aids to bridge the gap between PO releases to suppliers and production completion.

Focus on what matters!

Why you should care about your business processes? So, having determined that the On-time Delivery ("OTD") KPI is the best holistic operational performance measure, I needed to understand how it was possible that we were only satisfying customers only 76% of the time. I conducted a detailed review of every major supply chain and operational process within the company. I found that there were quite a few systems and business processes that were inefficient and needed improvement.

Areas that Needed Improvement

- **Over promise by sales team on delivery time** – Our problems started with sales promising customers a delivery date without any conversation with the Customer Service department. Sales and Operations teams struggled to meet the demand dates leading to a ripple effect downstream. Lack of clear policies and standard lead-times for both make-to-stock (MTS) and make-to-order (MTO) products was the first domino to fall.
 - **Training** – Poor training served to maintain our ISO certification, but was more form than substance, and it caused issues in virtually every functional area of our business. An emphasis on training is critical for Organization's success and its most effective when imparted on the job.
- 41** • **Standard Operating Procedures ("SOPs")** – Outdated and incorrect SOPs resulted in inconsistent management of inventory

and transactional errors. In fact, incorrect SOPs resulted in higher levels of scrap and out-of-spec products that were being rejected by the quality department. The process to main

- **Communication** – The lack of communication with shipping department led to shipping document inaccuracy, late pickup and packing errors. And negligence of shipping department further led to damage in transit.
- **Transparency in process** – Moreover, the lack of visibility to downtime and other operational delays further negatively impacted our ability to deliver on-time. These shortcomings drove a lack of consistency, repeatability and predictability.

Little Faith in Company’s Material Requirements Planning System – Lack of a sophisticated ERP

- A failure to maintain proper and timely planning parameters (lead times and safety stock levels) coupled with inaccurate sales forecasts resulted in production planning and procurement managers abandoning the company’s Material Requirements Planning (“MRP”) system and instead managing operations using “Tribal Knowledge” and gut instincts.
- Managing chemical operations using spreadsheets and gut instincts lead to other problems. The procurement manager approved purchase requests to buy material significantly in excess of what is required to meet the demand. This lead to a huge amount of capital being stuck due to this excess inventory.
- This same mentality existed in the production department, where rather than relying on SOPs, products were being manufactured from memory which led to production errors, inventory inaccuracy, poor quality and product rejections.

- This, of course, resulted in operators marching to the beat of their own drum and many variations in the products being delivered to quality for review.

Lack of Communication Between Associates

- When I considered the lack of well-defined business processes and faith in our systems, I began to believe that 76% On-time Delivery wasn't bad – How did we deliver anything on-time?
- It seemed like every order had a problem, causing a late delivery and an investigation always resulted in some culprit who was responsible for acting on their own and making assumptions, rather than following a prescribed, repeatable and consistent process.
- This promoted an environment that lacked trust, promoted finger-pointing and made it hard to communicate and act like a team.

Considering Root Cause Analysis (RCA) as a critical factor

- Whenever a failure or deviation occurs, there should be a proper infrastructure in place so that RCA can be done efficiently in an optimal duration.
- There should be a way to backtrack how the incident happened and capture the information i.e. in case of hardware failure there should be logs, archives, backups. There should be a way to capture and backtrack all business metrics responsible for the incident. Like a plane crash investigation, we should be able to backtrack and find what happened before seconds to disaster.

GOAL:

Ensure internal and external processes support the vision, Define to reality, align to operations, refine to vision

Define:

Document current process with team engagement

Workflow definitions (in-flow, out-flow, prioritization)

People, process and technology utilization

BlueBook baseline(1.0) delivery and prioritization

Align:

Current-state gap assessment

Prioritization of gaps through plan development

Execution assignments and planning (OTJ training)

BlueBook 2.0 delivery and process of updating

Refine:

Develop team norms and process

Execution of gaps and evolution assignments

Leadership and plan support

LACKINGS & IMPROVEMENTS

Online shopping and parcel delivery

The quality of parcel delivery has become extremely important as more and more people shop online. In the UK, 3 in every 4 adults made an online purchase in 2016, receiving in total over 1 billion parcels. By 2018, the e-commerce market is expected to grow by about one third, to reach 1.3 billion parcels annually. Cross-border shopping is also gaining pace as (in particular) younger consumers search and order goods online from other countries.

This growth in e-commerce means it's not surprising that consumers are more likely to experience problems with the delivery of their order than before. The near-collapse of the parcel delivery market around Christmas 2014 may have faded from public memory but it definitely spoilt that festive season for many customers when parcel companies seemed to lack enough vans and drivers to deliver all items on time.

Typical problems with **PARCEL ON TIME** delivery

Consumer surveys — including the latest study by Citizens Advice^[1] — reveal that as many as two thirds of consumers are likely to have experienced at least one problem with their online shopping parcel delivery in the past year. The most common problem is not a late or lost parcel, as one might think, but the problem of the no-one-at-home slip. This is the situation when the consumer is at home, sometimes having taken a day off to receive the parcel, but all she receives is a slip through the mailbox saying that “the parcel could not be delivered as there was no-one at home”. As a result, the consumer either has to arrange re-delivery or travel to a parcel depot which is often at an inconvenient location and/or is open at inconvenient hours to collect the parcel. Another frequent problem is the parcel being left in an unsecure location (even if the parcel is not damaged, it has clearly been put at risk). Problems with late, missing or lost parcels trail these other two in frequency.

Unless the delivery problem leads to financial loss, e.g. a damaged or lost parcel, most customers are not inclined to report the issue to the seller or the courier company. Hence, most problems that adversely affect consumer welfare due to lost time and stress, such as the no-one-at-home slip or leaving a parcel in an unsecure location (without damage), remain unknown to the seller/courier and are not properly addressed.

Possible solutions

The e-commerce market is responding by developing alternative delivery methods such as click-and-collect option, delivery at specified hours or on Saturday, and placing pick-up boxes/parcel lockers at convenient locations, e.g. a local supermarket.

Is there something else that can be done to reduce problems and improve consumer experience with parcel deliveries from online shopping? There are several possible policy options to consider.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

- the collection of data is secondary and is based on surveys & self observation
- the timely delivery and proper functioning varies time to time, the recent data shows its timely delivery operations and maybe in the future it may have some lacings or expected delivery delay
- the primary data observation based on my work experience in the company tells that it has a very good operation, but the reality in other warehouses may vary from my experience of warehouse in the “gurugram”

CONCLUSION

Concluding to the entire process, this was a necessary analysis to be done, and collection of data to the results will help us understand more about the importance of timely delivery and what flipkart do to maintain that.

As well as improve the cpd or customer promised date or timely delivery. also, the study shows the everyday challenges faced by flipkart to avoid cpd breach, unnecessary delay, and delivery faults like delivering to wrong address etc,

along with it maintaining timely delivery during festivals and rush hours and to keep up the user experience by deliverin fastest.

The concepts of next day delivery, 24 hour delivery, etc in tier 1 cities and making the product reach in the remotest village on time. This is indeed challenging but this literature will talk on all aspects of timely delivery to customers by flipkart and how they achieve this.

The customer centric approach of this literature will be useful for the reader to understand the processes

RECOMMENDATIONS

- To measure the quick delivery concept like 90 min delivery by flipkart
- How companies like blinkit achieve 10 min delivery and how flipkart can do the same
 - Other methods of delivery other than traditional delivery through courier boys
- Statistical analysis of order time, processing time & delivery time

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